

HR MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT MODEL FOR ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ONLINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Global competition and technological advances in Indonesia are circumvented by *Making Indonesia 4.0* including in the field of education. Finding a model for developing educators' HR management is an urgent need to be realized because of the turmoil in the post-pandemic education world. This study aims to find a model for developing educators' human resources in online learning for elementary schools in Gunungkidul. This research is designed with a *mix-method* approach, especially an *exploratory sequential* approach, which is to carry out a qualitative approach followed by quantitative. The research was conducted in Gunungkidul in 2021-2022 involving certain elementary schools. The hypothesis is found from a qualitative approach, followed by a quantitative approach to be tested with SEM to find the level of fixation of the founded model. This study found nine variables, namely; strategic planning in teacher management, strategic placement, school committee carrying capacity, principal supervision, reflection at the end of each learning activity, high dedication, the role of parental assistance in online learning, communicative in every implementation of online learning, ability to overcome online learning obstacles. The nine variables were analyzed with SEM and formed a model for developing educators' HR management in implementing online learning at the elementary school level. This model spurs teachers to adapt and improve to adjust towards the field conditions. Human resources who can secure the online learning process will be more useful in carrying out educational reforms, especially in online learning. The development of the educator HR management model found in this study provides useful theoretical contributions as a guide for implementing educator HR management in online learning in elementary schools both directly and indirectly related in Gunungkidul. Reliable educator human resources can realize effective online learning in elementary schools.

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INTRODUCTION

Industrial Revolution 4.0 in all corners of the world forces all lines of human life to change, one of which is human resources (Rasmitadila, Rusmiati *et al.*, 2020). Improving the quality of human resources is one of the 10 national priorities in *Making Indonesia 4.0* (Industry, 2018). Human capital in an organization, be it a company or a non-profit institution, is one of the intangible wealth which is almost 75% a source of wealth for companies or institutions (Noe *et al.*, 2014). On a large scale, the role of human resources is so dominant in a company. On a more specific scale, elementary school institutions, of course, human resources also play a very large role. Paying attention to the availability of superior human resources is an urgent demand for the existence of an institution. Similarly, in the field of education, human resources are the main support for the existence of a school.

Along with the increasingly globalized development of the era and demographics of population numbers and social dynamics, the development of elementary schools as an educational institution has experienced dramatic development. The government as the authority for providing education, especially in public schools, makes changes in policies for the efficiency and effectiveness of basic education. As technology accelerates, every school has the same challenges and opportunities. Schools as organizations must be able to adapt and try their best to serve the community as *stakeholders*. Organizations are always changing along with globalization, technological developments and employee dynamics (Fitz-etc, 2009).

The current challenge for leaders to their organizations is to ensure that the organization has a high-performance work system. Organizations have high performance when they are able to combine human and technological elements to maximize all elements of resources to achieve organizational targets (Noe *et al.*, 2014). None of these elements should be weakened. When there is a weakening or even stagnation, it means that there are some things related to policies, decisions that are not in accordance with the goals or targets of the organization.

Development of human resources in order to have high performance to make the school run effectively and be able to achieve the goals and vision-mission that have been set becomes urgent interests. Various efforts need to be made to make it happen. If the human resource development system stops, it is very likely that schools will stagnate, static and gradually shunned by the community. Various parties must work hand in hand to advance education in various ways. Schools, communities and governments must join hands together to cooperate with a variety of attractive and affordable programs.

Central and local governments have the responsibility of how people can get the right to education for their children. Central and regional policies greatly affect the continuity of learning both offline and online. In addition to the BOS fund that has been rolled out since long before the pandemic and flexible policies for handling COVID-19 prevention and implementing *online* learning as an effort to educate the nation's life.

At the end of 2019, *Covid-19* quickly spread to the entire surface of the earth, until the WHO declared it a global pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has created the biggest disruption to the education system in human history. This global pandemic has affected nearly 1.6 billion students in more than 200 countries around the world. The closure of schools, institutions, and other learning spaces has impacted more than 94% of the world's student population. Widespread changes are taking place in all aspects of life. Social distancing policies and restrictions on activities have disrupted educational practices. The reopening of schools after the easing of restrictions is another challenge with many new standard operating procedures put in place (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021).

When there is a pandemic that is still uncertain to date, the human resources of educators are also falling in realizing optimal services (Butterick & Charlwood, 2021; Gigauri, 2020). No less than 1.2 billion students worldwide leave their classes to avoid the spread of covid-19 at the discretion of the authorities (Li & Lalani, 2020). This forced the school to work on how learning could still take place even without face-to-face. With the advancement and sophistication of technology, *online* learning with all its advantages and disadvantages replaces face-to-face learning. Many factors affect the effectiveness of this online learning model.

From the school side, infrastructure greatly affects how they will carry out distance learning with the help of the internet. From the student side, those with all kinds of backgrounds (social, economic and geographical) influence the extent of response in the implementation of learning in this network. It is appropriate that the human resources in the school, in this case the principal and teachers, can break through with new creations that will boost learning outcomes in conditions that are still down.

Efforts to approach overcoming problems caused by this pandemic involve existing *multidisciplinary*, *multi-stakeholder-oriented*, *multilevel*, and *pluralist methodologies* (Caligiuri *et al.*, 2020). Involving multidisciplinary knowledge because it cannot only be from one side of science. Similarly, its users must involve all layers of users and policy makers at various levels. Thus, it is hoped that the right and accurate solution will be able to solve the problems that befall.

Human resources, whether as academics or practitioners, face choices. The choice is to want the future to continue with low HR management arrangements or bring change with reliable human resources to get out of complicated uncertain situations (Butterick & Charlwood, 2021).

Reliable personnel are immediately needed, those who can realize new breakthroughs in learning. Where conditions require that every face-to-face meeting be limited and tightened in order to maintain the health and safety of all parties. Even learning must continue without face-to-face. The second option is non-negotiable, according to the decision of the government as the authorities. This online meeting without face-to-face is absolute and the most realistic option.

This condition is indeed difficult, but distance or online learning innovations must be provided as much as possible. Of course, this is not an easy challenge for most elementary schools. This is because they were not used to doing this before the pandemic. They were previously used to face-to-face learning. This is one of the urgent challenges to immediately realize the right solution, accurate and maintain health protocols for all. How is the learning model in the network solutive and can be realized immediately in society at all levels.

Obstacles experienced by students, teachers and parents (Mar'ah *et al.* , 2020) In *online* teaching and learning activities, among others; mastery of technology that is still lacking, additional internet quota costs, additional work for parents in accompanying children to learn, communication and socialization between students, teachers and parents is reduced and working hours are not limited for teachers because they have to communicate and coordinate with parents, other teachers, and the principal.

The success of *online* learning in Indonesia (Rasmitadila, Rusmiati *et al.* , 2020) during the COVID-19 pandemic is determined by technological readiness in accordance with the national humanist curriculum, support and cooperation from all stakeholders, including the government, schools, teachers, parents, and the community. Teachers (Fauzi & Sastra Khusuma, 2020) understand the context of online learning, but in its implementation, various obstacles are found, including 1) availability of facilities, 2) use of networks and the internet, 3) planning, implementation, and evaluation of learning, and 4) cooperation with parents. Online learning helps teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic, but it is considered less effective, even 80% of teachers are not satisfied with carrying out *online* learning.

Is it true that the effectiveness of learning has an impact on the achievement and literacy of our children and adolescents? A literacy study titled '*World's Most Literate Nations*' announced in March 2016, a product of *Central Connecticut State University* (CCSU). Indonesia ranks 62 out of 70 countries. PISA research shows Indonesia's low literacy rate compared to countries in the world. This is the result of a study of 72 countries. The respondents were school children aged 15 years, the number was around 540 thousand children (Damarjati, 2019). Despite some rebuttals to the conclusions of the study, effective schools are fundamental to realizing quality education.

Various pedagogy has been designed for online learning. Teachers who fall behind in technology need training for the improvement of competencies oriented towards their students. Authentic assessment and appropriate feedback are important components of learning. A very important part of distance learning (online) is the availability of helpful formative assessments and appropriate feedback to learners online (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021).

The effectiveness of school organization has been identified as one of the most important factors for future educational success. Organizational effectiveness is closely related to students' achievement and attitudes towards school (Bhuyan, 2018). The role of the principal, leadership, school culture plays a role in the long-term sustainability of educational effectiveness (Bellei *et al.* , 2019) . Some schools have school effectiveness with comparisons based on the socioeconomic status of students in the school (Akay & Aypay, 2016). Behaviors and habits based on social status have an impact on how schools will have different effectiveness. This can be a guide for how schools that have not been effective to adjust the treatment or behavior that exists in schools.

School effectiveness is also closely related to the effectiveness of the principal's leadership and teacher job satisfaction (Kauts & Sharma, 2017). The effectiveness of the principal's leadership impacts in many ways. One of them is teacher satisfaction with the principal's leadership. From there the effectiveness of the school is built by compact joint work. The effectiveness of this school cannot be separated from the success of effective human resource development as well.

Adequate working environment conditions, skilled resources, and when a sense of organizational identity and purpose are always upheld, come together and bring a sense of unity to the community. This is something that is coveted. When this is not the case, the impact on the school climate and internal work processes will be readily apparent. A decline in these aspects reduces academic effectiveness and leads to a lack of confidence. Maintaining a high level of stability in leadership teamwork orientation is relevant to maintaining effectiveness (Bellei *et al.* , 2019) .

The uncertainty that occurs due to the pandemic that has an impact on human resources must be found a solution (Harney & Collings, 2021). This is certainly something urgent so that educational goals, especially at

the elementary school level, can get a way out. How solutions must be raised to bridge the deadlock of face-to-face learning so that the content of education both knowledge, attitudes and skills can be achieved by students.

Based on some of these explanations, further research needs to be carried out to what extent the effectiveness of the implementation of online learning in students, especially in elementary schools. Some schools that have been implementing online learning since before the pandemic have found benefits and effectiveness in learning.

The existence of future human resources has become a hot topic for researchers, how their future is related to globalizing human resources and the skills they have. Will they be displaced and lose their jobs (Harney & Collings, 2021). This is an anxiety in itself. The extent to which the existence of schools with online models will shift the existence of teachers. Conservative teachers are displaced by technology, so that only teachers with certain abilities will have the opportunity to be teachers who exist in uncertain times. This is a big problem in the management of educators. The need for schools using technology is inevitable as it is today.

Seeing the development of HR management strategies, especially in online learning in elementary schools, it is important for a model that is extracted from empirical experience to be used as a reference in the implementation of educator HR management in online learning in elementary schools. The discovery of factors that directly or indirectly influence the tested HR management in the implementation of online learning is very important. It was this discovery of potential that became the basis of this research.

2. METHODOLOGY

Combination research method is an approach in research that combines quantitative and qualitative research methods in collecting and analyzing data (John W. Cresswell, 2009; Sekaran & Roger, 2016). *Sequential exploratory* design was used in this study, namely conducting qualitative research first and then quantitative. This approach shows the researcher doing two different approaches sequentially. With this design, at the initial stage obtained are findings that are hypotheses which are then continued with testing these hypotheses in similar schools that have been determined.

Qualitative methods are able to find hypotheses in certain cases or phenomena on a limited sample. Furthermore, quantitative methods are used to test hypotheses in a wider population. So this method is useful for finding hypotheses and at the same time proving the external validity of these hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2018).

Data collected from questionnaires given to respondents, then processed to be tested using SEM (*Structural Equation Modelling*). Analysis using SEM is able to test the findings of the new model integrally resulting from this study.

A statistical analysis of field findings from this *mixed methods* approach research. The results of the analysis of the model's findings are discussed and interpreted in accordance with research rules to draw conclusions and recommendations.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

With a qualitative approach, find several variables that after being analyzed and ready to be analyzed on SEM to find a fix for the model formed. These variables include; strategic planning in teacher management, strategic placement, school committee carrying capacity, principal supervision, reflection at the end of each learning activity, high dedication, the role of parental assistance in online learning, communicative in every implementation of online learning, Ability to overcome online learning obstacles.

The statistical analysis produces as presented below.

Tabel 1: Regression of the independent variable to the dependent variable

Variable	Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Role	<--- Planning	-.281	.111	-2.522	.012
Role	<--- Daya_Dukung	-.064	.146	-.434	.664
Role	<--- Supervision	.316	.158	1.994	.046
Communicative	<--- Supervision	-.049	.096	-.514	.608
Ability	<--- Reflection	4.478	4.546	.985	.325
Ability	<--- Dedication	-.540	4.109	-.132	.895
Communicative	<--- Reflection	.633	.136	4.643	***
Role	<--- Placement	1.219	.409	2.980	.003
Management	<--- Role	-.086	1.139	-.076	.940
Management	<--- Communicative	-.118	1.700	-.069	.945
Management	<--- Ability	.739	.053	13.814	***

- 1) There is a significant and significant relationship between strategic planning in teacher management and the role of parental assistance in online learning, namely r^2 of -0.281 with a probability of 0.012 .
- 2) There is a positive and significant relationship between strategic placement and parental assistance in online learning, namely r^2 of 1.219 with a probability of 0.003 .
- 3) There is a negative and insignificant relationship between the carrying capacity of the school committee and the role of parental assistance in online learning, namely r^2 of -0.064 and probability of 0.664 .
- 4) There is a positive and significant relationship between the principal's supervision and parental assistance in online learning, namely r^2 of 0.316 with a probability of 0.046 .
- 5) There is a negative and insignificant relationship between the principal's supervision and communicative in each online learning implementation with r^2 of -0.049 with a probability of 0.608 .
- 6) There is a positive and significant relationship between reflection at the end of each learning activity and communicative in each online learning implementation with r^2 of 0.633 with a probability of 0.000 .
- 7) There is a positive and insignificant relationship between reflection at the end of each learning activity with the ability to overcome online learning obstacles with r^2 of 4.478 with a probability of 0.325 .
- 8) There is a negative and insignificant relationship between high dedication and ability to overcome online learning obstacles with r^2 of -0.540 with a probability of 0.895 .
- 9) There is a negative and insignificant relationship between the role of parental assistance in online learning and the management of elementary school online learning human resources with r^2 of -0.086 with a probability of 0.940 .
- 10) There is a negative and insignificant relationship between communicative in each implementation of online learning and the management of elementary school online learning human resources with r^2 of -0.118 with a probability of 0.945 .
- 11) There is a positive and significant relationship between the ability to overcome online learning constraints and the management of elementary school online learning human resources with r^2 of 0.739 with a probability of 0.000 .

Tabel 2: Model Fit Summary

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	85	792.018	380	.000	2.084
Saturated model	465	.000	0		
Independence model	30	5993.989	435	.000	13.779

Model Fit Summary, CMIN shows how good the existing model is. To determine whether or not a model is good in terms of the default CMIN value of the model, if the *default* CMIN value of the model is between the *CMIN Saturated* model and the *independent model*, then the model can be said to be good. In the CMIN table above, you can see the value of the CMIN Default model 792.018 which is between the *CMIN Saturated* model and the *Independent* model, which means it shows that the *model is good*. However, if you look at the probability value (p) which is 0.000 far below 0.05 (alpha 5%) means that the model is less fit.

Tabel 3: RMR, GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)

Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI
Default model	.543	.849	.815	.694
Saturated model	.000	1.000		
Independence model	13.532	.195	.139	.182

RMR, GFI and AGFI values range from 0 to 1. For the RMR value, the smaller the RMR value, the better the model (fit), while for GFI and AGFI the greater the value, the better the model. From the table, it can be seen that the RMR value of 0.543 is a bit far above 0 but the GFI value of 0.849 and AGFI 0.815 are already quite high, thus it can be said that the model is able to explain the existing data or the model can be said to be feasible.

Tabel 4: Baseline Comparisons

Model	NFIDelta1	RFIrho1	IFIDelta2	TLIrho2	CFI
Default model	.868	.849	.927	.915	.926
Saturated model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Independence model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Baseline Comparisons show the value of NFI (Normed of Fit Index), RFI (Relative Fit Index), IFI (Incremental Fit Index) and CFI (*Comparative Fit Index*) which have a range of values from 0 to 1, while TLI values can be minus to above 1. All measuring instruments on *baseline comparisons* have the same function, namely to see whether the model is fit with existing data or not. The NFI, RFI, IFI and CFI values are closer to 1, the model is more fit with the existing data. Looking at the data above, that the value is close to 1 means that the model is fit.

Tabel 5: RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)

Model	RMSEA	THE 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default model	.060	.054	.066	.003
Independence model	.206	.202	.211	.000

The RMSEA value indicates whether the model is fit with the existing data or not. A good RMSEA is if the value is below 0.05 which indicates the model is really fit with the existing data. The RMSEA value is still above 0.05 (0.060) but is close to that value, the model can still be said to be fit with the existing data. This can be said to have a tendency or tendency, so it can be said that the model can be tolerated.

Tabel 6. HOELTER

Model	HOELTER.05	HOELTER.01
Default model	162	170
Independence model	25	26

(Hoelster) The above shows whether the model is fit with the existing data or not. As a rule of thumb, if the *Hoelster* value is greater than 200, then it can be said that the model is fit with the existing data. In the calculation table the value of *Hoelster* 162 for alpha 5% and 170 for alpha 1%, which means that the data is not yet fit but still has a tendency. *Hoelster's* value is close to the value of 200, the model is not yet fit properly, but still tolerable, the model is acceptable. After considering several standard fixes of a model, ranging from *CMIN*, *RMR*, *GFI*, *Baseline comparisons*, *RMSEA*, and *HOELTER* shows that the model is accepted with existing data.

The ability to overcome obstacles in online learning is the only variable in this study that has a direct influence on HR management in online learning. Below are described several dimensions that show indicators that the ability to overcome obstacles has a positive and significant effect on online learning management.

Teachers always reflect in online learning. Teachers are able to identify deficiencies in each online learning activity. With this ability to reflect, it can then improve some of the strengths in online learning. Existing shortcomings are communicated by teachers to students or parents. They also realize and feel that they are getting meaningful learning.

Teachers always identify obstacles experienced by students in responding to online learning. In this case, the teacher must be really observant and attentive to each learner. The inactivity of students is very likely caused by technical obstacles faced. With attention in such matters, teachers always try to respond positively to every response of inactive learners.

Teachers are always looking for solutions to every obstacle in online learning that arises in implementation. By finding solutions with the online team, all obstacles and complaints can be resolved. With a solution from the teacher, students get meaningful learning services. It is this meaningful learning that makes knowledge, understanding and skills complete the competencies set in learning. Teachers as educators must always do various tricks so that students do not get bored. Students are able to accept learning with the right approach and maximum results.

Educators innovate as much as they can to improve the implementation of online learning. Every innovation always fosters the enthusiasm of teachers to continue to work in order to improve teaching capacity which has an impact on students' meaningfulness in learning. Students will be able to enjoy the innovations created by teachers enthusiastically, as long as the teacher is able to bring innovations with full enthusiasm and of course readiness to implement them. Innovation in carrying out this learning task as long as it is still related to learning objectives or learning outcomes, it will be as expected.

In relation to innovation or creation carried out, teachers must get additional improvements in learning outcomes. Thus teachers can also provide practical solutions to every obstacle experienced by students. In online learning, there are always students who need practical guidance on the obstacles or problems faced. Without a solution given to students, it is tantamount to increasing student confusion in learning. The solutions provided by the teacher do not always have to be something practical, but also things that will encourage students to create and innovate. Students need to get space to express what is on their minds during learning. This flexibility will constantly challenge students to accelerate their abilities.

Educators do various tricks so that students can easily follow online learning either *syncron* (direct) or *asyincron* (indirect). When teachers carry out learning with students with *zoom meetings* or *g-meet* or other applications that can be used for direct online learning. The opportunity to meet directly allows teachers to be able to read students' mimic movements that show students' identity in responding to learning. As for indirect online learning, teachers can provide clear and directed instructions.

The ability of educators to instill an independent and honest attitude is something that educators must strive for competence. When educators complain about participants lacking independence and honesty, the opposite is true. Educators must have a way and practice to instill independence and honesty. This is a challenge for educators. Independent and honest are among the characteristics that become the goal of learning, including online learning.

The readiness of educators in facing uncertain conditions must be prepared early. This is where the core value of the importance of educators' ability to overcome obstacles and limitations. Obstacles can actually be described both personal constraints and the surrounding environment. Obstacles can be caused by personal limitations or environmental limitations. When educators are able to overcome obstacles and limitations, many things to improve the quality of online learning will be achieved. School resource management needs to pay attention to and implement programs related to the capacity and quality of educators in providing maximum online learning. Similar activities are a necessity that is continuously pursued so that each individual educator is independently able to realize the success of online learning.

4. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

There are nine independent variables found in the qualitative approach which are then formed hypotheses and tested with SEM so that a management model of elementary school educators in online learning is formed. The nine variables are; Human resource management in online learning namely: strategic planning in teacher management, strategic placement, school committee carrying capacity, principal supervision, reflection at the end of each learning activity, high dedication, the role of parental assistance in online learning, Communicative in every implementation of online learning, the ability to overcome online learning obstacles.

1. The combination of independent variables forms a new model that has a direct or indirect relationship to human resource management, especially educators. From the relationship between

- variables that make up a new model, there is one variable that has a direct effect on human resource management (educators), namely the ability to overcome online learning obstacles.
2. The new model found has five positive and significant associations, namely;
 - a. Strategic planning in teacher management affects the role of parental assistance in online learning. It is necessary to strengthen the relationship between parents and teachers to increase children's learning participation. Parents and teachers are an integral part of online learning at the elementary school level, cooperation between two parties will have an impact on children's learning.
 - b. The principal's vision influences the role of parental assistance in online learning. The principal and parents have a harmonious relationship in improving the quality of learning and parental participation in students. The policies and approaches that the school implements on students condition the school to implement policies to achieve school goals.
 - c. Reflection at the end of each learning activity affects communicative in every implementation of online learning. With reflection presents positive feedback for the improvement of the implementation of learning next.
 - d. Strategic placement affects the role of parental assistance in online learning. The placement of teacher human resources has an inseparable intersection with parental satisfaction in the learning experienced by their students,
 - e. The ability to overcome obstacles in online learning affects the HR management of educators. The peak of teachers' human resources is when they are ready for global changes that always demand improving the abilities and services carried out by teacher.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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